

Smart Robotic Prostheses using Deep Learning And Musculoskeletal Modeling

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Keywords:

1. Introduction

Robots are revolutionising the field of prosthetics. With the application of machine learning, prosthetic rehabilitation can become more natural in terms of performance and sustainable for human anatomy.

2. Aim

To develop Smart Robotic Prostheses using Deep Learning by investigating the human activity of scooping various forms of materials using Musculoskeletal Modeling

3. Material and methods

In this study, the human activity of scooping various forms of materials is investigated. The activity is divided in different motion primitives. For each primitive, human right arm degree of freedom to jaco human skill is analysed in terms of physiological parameters, including wrist pronation-supination angle, elbow flexion angle, shoulder rotation/abduction/flexion angles, hand acceleration, and wrist pronation angular velocity. Optimum human posture is identified for each primitive in terms of muscular effort using musculoskeletal modelling. This analysis identifies how humans execute same activity for the different types of materials. Each human motion primitive is mapped to robotic arm primitive for efficient execution for different materials. The 6 DOF robotic arm is equipped with a camera to capture the image of the material which it has to scoop. The robot is programmed using a deep convolutional neural network, which is trained to identify the type of material using machine vision.

4. Results

Expected Results: The robot would scoop the given material by identifying its type through camera and perform the scooping activity like we humans do using the musculoskeletal parameters .

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❖ Research Architecture

Figure 1:

5. Conclusions

This perspective research fully utilises the mechanical potential of robots within the constraints of human musculoskeletal system.

6. Key words

Robotics, Deep Learning, Musculoskeletal Modeling, Prostheses